

Staging the Christian Theatre: A Review of Bayo Afolabi's *Ascend*

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Synopsis

Ascend, written and directed by Bayo Afolabi for the 20th convocation play of the Redeemer's University of Nigeria, Ede, is a good attempt at the presentation of another Christian-themed performance at the BOJA Arts Theatre. The story gives life to the thoughts and actions of Lucifer, named 'Lucifero' for dramatic context, following his outlaw from heaven due to rebellion, and his plan to take out his unsuccessful coup on mankind. Now ruthless, seeks several ways together with his league of dedicated fallen angels to distract mankind from the heavenly race, using several random schemes. Lucifero, in his monologue confesses to be the brain behind the several distractions, immoral decay, lusts, rivalry, wars, and several other unfortunate incidents ravaging the world today; claiming the souls of saints. The play climaxes with the symbolic presentation of hell and heaven scenes where the unrighteous and the righteous were welcomed and judged according to their works.

Performance Review

Acting and Music

The team gave an excellent display of acting and singing skills –the major drivers for the communication of the story. The actors which were a mixture of undergraduate and postgraduate students embodied their character well enough and they certainly deserve their flowers for the great energy. The well-layered use of songs throughout the play, especially hymns assisted in propelling the plot forward and particularly became the solar plexus recalibrating the focus of the play at intervals.

Christian-themed Performance

The performance passes as a 'Christian-themed performance' but barely fits perfectly into the idea of the Christian theatre¹. Instead, it presented Christian-centred themes conveyed through sarcasms, flowery words, and overly layered with funny witty statements. It made no attempt at achieving reconciliation of the human souls seated in the audience, while also exposing the performers to a potential risk of undermining the work of salvation.

Biblical Hermeneutics

The performance which kick-started with high spirits following the brief presentation of percussion instrumentalists who almost brought the roof down with a thrilling performance, started well with rumblings and sporadic gunshots to symbolize chaos, with several people, who would later be known as fallen angels, dressed in black darting around the stage under strobe lights. This happened to herald the appearance of Lucifero and his aid who later emerged looking defeated due to the unsuccessful coup perceived to have happened offstage.

¹ Olatunji and Oki describes it as the practice of theatre by genuine Christians for the proliferation of the gospel message and the (re)connection of human souls to God... "Creating the Contemporary Christian Theatre: An X-Ray of Sight & Sound Theatres", *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol 6, Issue 2, 2024. p. 70.
<https://www.garjc.com/articles/636/>

However, an eye for detail would easily fault this scene to be inconsistent because the war that broke out in heaven was not explained to be a war of guns, neither was Lucifer described as beggarly despite his outlaw from heaven but as the 'great' dragon². This identifies the issue of inconsistent Biblical dramatization and inappropriate costuming right from the opening scene. For the sake of audience attention, and especially for an opening scene, it would have worked better if the war was imitated than imagined, and for the costume to have done justice to the principal character, Lucifero, and the fallen 'angels' on their first introduction.

Biblical Doctrine

Biblical doctrine is the soul of Christian drama and theatre, when absent or wrongly presented, it exposes the plotline to the risk of inflicting corruption and ultimately causing death³. In *Ascend*, there were a few scenes that negated the focus of biblical doctrines by passively giving expression to the doctrine of harmitiology (sin) in the following ways:

- a. *Overt Enactment and Communication of Sexual Issues* –While trying to identify the anomalies in the society and Christian faith, there was too much focus on the art of sexualizing than using the issues identified to cause repentance. This is because it takes actions and words to create mental pictures hence, the route the miscommunication took will certainly leave some of the audience mesmerized and aroused during or after the scenes even though they sheepishly laughed it off. The tendency of this happening is high because such occurrences happened repeatedly, hence capable of sowing seeds of lust instead of repentance.
- b. *Ridiculing the Horrors of Hell* –The entire hell scene did not communicate regret, nor spark repentance. There were still unnecessary funky dialogues and sarcasm. Hence, passively communicating to people that hell isn't as bad as it seems. Eschatology which should be the heart of every Christian message should not be a theme for sarcasm.
- c. *Breaking God's Structure of Cause and Effects* –The soul that sins shall die but of course there is an open window of mercy in the presence of repentance. In the process of journeying to the Golden City, an old man was portrayed to desire having immoral contacts with the nun sisters that accommodated him alongside some others. Although he did not execute it because he was not afforded the opportunity to but he desired it. Eventually he became the reason they were sent away from the monastery and there was no sign of remorse or repentance from the man. But the next appearance of the old man was in heaven wearing a white and gold garment alongside the others. That is heretic! It is dangerous because, to someone in the audience, that may preach the sermon of 'once saved, forever saved', and blur out the grievous consequences of falling into lust. The old man could have been portrayed to have repented before the following scene. This is not to provide some justification for him but to protect the spiritual nurturing of the audience which ought to happen through proper priesthood.

Design

For every theatrical performance, irrespective of the efforts put into the audio methods like music and acting, the complementary features of the visuals (design) cannot be underemphasized as contemporary audiences want to be thrilled while unraveling the story. As discussed by Ojo and

² See Revelations 12:7-9

³ Jones Profit emphasized the essence of theological balance with artistic expression where aesthetics is present with every thematic portrayal on the stage in order to appeal to and engage the audience proactively without compromising the integrity of the message being conveyed. "A Methodological Review of Mike Bamiloje's Concept of Christian Drama". *African Journal of Religious and Theological Studies*, Vol. 3, No. 1, 2025. p. 90.
<https://doi.org/10.62154/ajrts.2025.03.010719>

Olatunji, priority should be given to audience attention and engagement in the theatre above mere attendance⁴. Their study identifies aesthetic communication as a solution to the age long problem capable of achieving an immersive theatre experience and deriving undivided audience attention. It further places emphasis on the methods of achieving audience attention in the production right from the exposition of the story to the curtain call using elements of aesthetic communication. However, in *Ascend*, the elements of design were almost absent and the few used were meagerly represented. The design was too basic and symbolic for a command performance discussing random themes revolving from glamour to terror and honour.

- a. Due to the inappropriate use of costumes, the audience could not visualize what it looked like when the devil actually descended into the world. Was he looking horrific? Was he immediately wearing a black and red like some Nollywood movies have wrongly misrepresented? Lucifero's garb did not do justice.
- b. Similarly, the set and props were majorly symbolic and almost absent hence depriving the audience of the aesthetic satisfaction they should have derived from 'watching' the play. But since the acting was good, it would have passed as an excellent audio drama, and doubtlessly the audiences would fill in the gap on their own with cinematic, aesthetic and complementing visuals according to their level of aesthetic taste and exposure.

The Mixed-Media Directing Technique

The contemporary theatre now tilts towards the use of mixed-media in performance as one of the effective methods of assisting the communication of the dramatic story while also sustaining audience attention and patronage. It is the use of various media forms within a single medium. As the theatre is a single medium (stage medium) that engages the use of basic elements – actors, costumes, designers, and lights, mixed-media in theatre directing denotes the additional use of technological gadgets and media elements that are external to the stage medium within the live stage performance to aid textual interpretation, enhance performance and sustain audience attention⁵. The artistic director of *Ascend* made an attempt to use the mixed-media technique through the use of a table projector device but it was underused for the display of few background images that were mostly silhouetted when actors past the rays.

First, the world is fast evolving and creativity becomes the new economy⁶, therefore, it looks archaic to use table projectors for performances especially if they are not properly hung in a way designed for performance. Secondly, the mixed-media technique is not limited to image projection and sound effects but extends to other concepts like Mediation –the act of transmitting through a mechanism that serves as an intermediary between one and the other; Mediatisation –the process of shaping the human perception of modernity and meaning through the provisions of the media; using media technologies (film, lighting, sound, and interactive costumes, to mention a few) to create the aesthetics and performance quality by providing an experience of the world based on mechanical, technological, or electronic media, all of which the audiences are used to; and Digitization –an extension of the basic theatre practice by attracting a large number of audiences to a digital environment and, in turn, establishing the theatre in an unlimited virtual space patronised by billions of people.

⁴ Ojo, Abayomi and Olatunji, Olalekan. "Theatrical Performance and Aesthetic Communication in Darkest Night Directed by Festus Dairo". *SCHOLARS: Journal of Arts & Humanities*. Volume 5, No. 2, 2023. p. 74.
<https://doi.org/10.3126/sjah.v5i2.57501>

⁵ See Olatunji, Olalekan. "Mixed-Media Directing Technique and the Salvation of Theatre-Going Culture: The Aesthetics of Contemporary Theatre in Nigeria". *Academia Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences*, Vol. 2, 2025. p. 237.
<https://doi.org/10.3126/ajhss.v2i1.79258>

⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 242.

Therefore, as commendable as the attempt with the mixed-media technique was in *Ascend*, it was ineffective in the context of its design as audience attention was not sustained and audience patronage threatened due to the fall in aesthetic quality and supply.

Recommendation

Fundamentally, the theatre remains a seeing place. For Christian theatre, the intention is more focused on the reconnection of human souls to God but the techniques to achieve this result are similar when compared to commercial theatres. Therefore, if effective communication will be achieved, the Christian theatre, must play by the rules, not excusing techniques with spirituality, and not expecting pardon when the potential souls to be saved will begin their journey to salvation through an excellent performance experience.